

Original Research Article

A Story of Mathematics and Sports: Significant Events in the Evolution of a Trans Man

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ABSTRACT: This autoethnographic narrative presents significant events during my journey into secondary mathematics teaching and coaching, concurrent with my life as a trans man. Masculinity, athleticism, and mathematics have been three of the most influential threads of my life, and I see them as interrelated. The goal of this autoethnography is to explore those connections and illuminate some aspects of masculinity that intrude into the field of mathematics education. I begin with my experiences as an elementary student athlete in the K-12 education system and then move the narrative into my diagnosis as a trans boy. Finally, I discuss the impacts that gender had on my teaching and coaching career once I decided to live authentically as a trans man—an identity that is currently under attack in particularly vicious ways.

KEYWORDS: *autoethnography; trans; mathematics; sports*

Our life is made of experiences, but those experiences are made up of people. And while parents obviously play an integral role, unless your child is living in a cave they are interacting with other adults in their day-to-day lives. They learn a lot from their parents to be sure, but those beliefs are reinforced, challenged, or amended from years of working with teachers and other authority figures. (Hunsicker, 2010)

Introduction: Identity, Community, and Context

There are events in our lives where we move from a space of not knowing how to do something to knowing. I can specifically remember when I realized how factoring by grouping worked during Advanced Placement Calculus. I had been using the concept for a couple of years just by following the process, but suddenly, I understood why the process worked. I do not remember learning how to ride a bike, or swim. Both of those athletic achievements seem to be something I was just born doing. In my memory, I could always ride a bike and I could always swim. I was often told as a child that I was athletic, and feeling like I was born knowing how to do those two activities further grounded my identity as an athlete.

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Received: 9 January 2023 / Revised: 29 September 2023 / Published: 5 November 2023

I can also remember suddenly knowing I wanted to be a math teacher and coach, exactly like my mentor. I had not been sure about going to college (the Coast Guard seemed like a better fit) but then he pointed out that I could continue both playing sports and learning mathematics, my two favorite activities. After four years to gain my Bachelor of Arts in mathematics and another two years to gain my Master of Arts in mathematics education, my teaching and coaching career started.

I am currently a queer, trans man with a Ph.D. in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) Education. I use queer to describe my sexuality, and I define it to mean I am not attracted to one singular type of sexuality or gender. Instead, I feel attraction to people more based on how we interact and my tendency to feel intellectually challenged. I use trans to mean that I identify as a man even though I was assigned female at birth. Essentially, I have always felt more masculine than feminine, more boy than girl, and more man than woman.

During my childhood, I lived in a suburb of a large Midwestern city where I completed my public, K-12 schooling and participated on local youth and school sports teams. After graduating high school in 1990, I attended a small liberal arts college in a rural, small city with a population of about 17,000 people where I earned my Bachelor of Arts in mathematics and competed on the varsity softball team. I started my transition in the summer of 2012 while teaching at the high school where I was employed as a teacher for 15 years and coach for 10 years. The school district was in an area that was liberal enough to have an ordinance with employment protections in place for the LGBTQ+ community (Jost, 2013) but was conservative enough that when President Obama gave his “Back to School Speech” in 2009, the teachers were not allowed to show it to their classes. This dichotomy of political ideology stemmed from the town being heavily influenced by the more progressive leaning university population while the surrounding rural areas, though fewer in number, were loud enough to create a conservative atmosphere in the K-12 schools.

I am currently an assistant professor at a mid-sized, liberal arts university in the upper Midwest of the United States. However, having taught public school, secondary mathematics and science for 18 years, and coaching softball for 15 years, I firmly identify as a teacher and a coach. For all those years, I would arrive to school early to have the classroom ready. My classroom was unique for a math teacher as my walls held the numerous plaques the softball team I coached had won, along with motivational and Albert Einstein posters. I also had a bookshelf full of both fiction and non-fiction that my students were allowed to borrow if they wanted something to read, along with numerous chess boards and physical puzzles where a person tries to remove a ring.

For my students, it was common knowledge that topics outside of mathematics and softball could be discussed in the classroom, on the practice field, or on bus rides. My students and players would often ask me questions that ranged from simple tutoring requests to advice about which college to attend. Through these conversations, I built rapport with students and players that moved beyond educational norms, and occasionally I would offer up thoughts and critical questions about topics many teachers would avoid such as politics, gay rights, and abortion.

For example, one day during a softball practice while I was coaching, a couple of players started talking about another student at school.

One of the players said, “She has LT.”

The second player replied, “What is LT?”

And the first player responded, “Lesbian tendencies.”

I stopped and asked the first player to describe what people mean when they use a phrase like “lesbian tendencies,” and after thinking for a second the player said, “Well, you know, short hair, kind of acts like a guy, aggressive.” I said, “You mean like a softball player?” Both players laughed

and went on with their skills work, but they did get the point and I did not hear them use that phrasing again.

Another, more significant situation happened in 2003 when a memorial for a soldier was held in the school district's auditorium. Given the rural location of the district, our school never believed we would be a place for protests. However, the Westboro Baptist Church from Topeka, Kansas showed up to picket and held up signs that read, "God Hates Fags." After the memorial, during class the following day, a student asked me, "Would you ever picket a funeral?" The class grew silent waiting for my response: "No, absolutely not. But if that is a topic you all want to discuss, we can."

These types of scenarios were important to my style of teaching and coaching, and throughout this article I will describe some life events (which I remember as primarily emotional) that contributed to my development as a trans man. My journey is unique in that mathematics and sports are traditionally heterosexual and masculine topics (Ahlqvist et al., 2013; Ellison & Swanson, 2010; Reay, 2001; Yeh & Rubel, 2020) and K-12 public schools, including athletic teams, are not inviting systems for the LGBTQ+ community (Blount, 2005; Rands, 2009; Connell, 2015).

Methodology

This research is being conducted as a narrative autoethnography (Chang, 2008) because I am studying my experiences in relation to the society and culture in which I was living. Narrative autoethnography is an appropriate methodology because I am providing an in-depth look at my experiences as a trans man, secondary mathematics teacher and hoping that by sharing my story, I help to improve the world around me (Adams & Holman Jones, 2011). According to Chang (2008), narrative autoethnographies "commonly mix different writing styles in one text" (p. 149), and my narrative is a combination of descriptive-realist and analytical-interpretive writing (Chang, 2008). However, I also write from a queer perspective to tell my story that would otherwise be "shrouded in silence" and with the hope of "making discursive" trouble (Adams & Holman Jones, 2011). Throughout the paper I will "depict places, people, experiences, and events as accurately as possible" (Chang, 2008, p. 143), and I will also discuss social norms for the geographical areas in the given time periods (Chang, 2008). This combination will provide for the most authentic representation of my path.

Data Analysis

The data used for the research included photos, newspapers, yearbooks, report cards, and various pamphlets from special events throughout my life. I used the data to find places in my life where my mathematics and athlete identities, and my trans man identity, intersect in key moments and used the items to elicit memories and emotions associated with the event. As I used the photos in particular, I was careful to note my positionality within the photo and what that photo indicated about me at that time in my life.

Emergent Findings

In the following section, three significant life events of mine are highlighted in chronological order to show my development as a trans man and a mathematics teacher and coach. The events were selected as key moments from my childhood, adolescence, and adulthood. I will describe the oftentimes joyous or painful memories and emotions associated with the experiences and their relevance to my journey.

Childhood

Everyone has various characteristics or aspects of themselves they consider to be a part of their identity formed through a complex emotional and social process. Some of those aspects are connected through societal performances or narratives (Gee, 2000; Sfard & Prusak, 2005; Butler, 2007) while others are a part of person's nature. From my early childhood until about age 12, I consistently identified as a boy and was happy to engage in a male performance with my short hair and athleticism.

Around age 4 I asked my mom during a quiet moment, "When will I get my penis?"

She replied, "You do not have a penis, honey, you have a vagina."

I said, "But someday I will get my penis because I keep wishing for one. And when I get it, I'm going to need to know my boy's name. What is my boy's name?"

My mom replied, "Kyle Stephen. That is what we would have named if you had been born a boy."

I never let go of the joyous day that I would be called Kyle.

During this youthful time, when I was with my friends, I was just one of the guys, playing baseball, shooting b-b guns, building treehouses, and playing Capture the Flag. On the playground at recess, I was often chosen as the captain of one of the teams. The male acceptance I gained from my peers throughout this stage extended to adults who often mistook me for a boy, and I was only too happy to wear that label. When women in designated restrooms said to me, "Young man, get out of this bathroom. You know you don't belong in here," I was only too happy to leave. I did not belong there anyway and felt that woman had given me permission to use boys' restrooms.

One could say that my athletic career began with tee baseball as my first organized sport. The team was composed of children ages five and six who lived in the same neighborhood with no segregation for gender. I remember very distinctly demanding to get number five on my uniform (just a t-shirt) because

Figure 1. Kyle Whipple, age 1, Table Rock Lake, Missouri

Figure 2. Kyle Whipple, age 6, Blue Springs Softball Association

when I grew up, I wanted to be George Brett. The coach of the team quickly noted that I was the only player capable of throwing the baseball from third base to first base and encouraged that dream. I really enjoyed playing the game and quickly distinguished myself as someone who understood the rules and could stand out as an athlete by completing an unassisted triple play. This combination, of being able to strategize and being athletic, led to me being placed on numerous all-star teams through my childhood, each opportunity reinforcing my masculine traits.

Figure 3. Kyle Whipple, age 7, Blue Springs Youth Soccer League

In school, disrupting the gender norms and being read as male gave me permission to excel in mathematics and I used it to my advantage as soon as I started school. I have a specific memory of sitting in a chair directly in front of my third-grade teacher while she moved through multiplication flashcards with me giving the answers. I see “8x8” on the card and I quickly respond, “64.” The teacher announces loud enough for the class to hear, “Well done, you may move your name to the center of the bullseye. You have mastered your multiplication facts.” Knowing these math facts made both the teacher and me proud; she was proud I had been one of the first students in class to correctly complete my multiplication tables in the allotted time, and I was proud because I had even further cemented my gender identity as male when I was publicly rewarded for succeeding in a subject area that was primarily dominated by the boys in the school. Those types of mathematical experiences would continue for me throughout elementary school. When in sixth grade the students were offered the opportunity to work at our own pace, I and two other boys finished the textbook well before the end of the school year. As a reward, we were allowed to play role playing games in the back of the classroom for the remainder of the school year.

My experience of attempting to establish my own identity this early in my life as a trans man was colliding with the existing social and cultural norms of gender identities. Sveningsson & Alversson (2003) suggest that social and cultural establishments, such as schools and communities, work on the myth of a single, fixed, and stable identity. Yet, my actions as a youth were disrupting the stable identity concept. Furthermore,

Article continues on the next page.

my deliberate actions of becoming a “math geek,” “jock,” or using boys’ bathrooms were showing how social norms and institutions affected my early journey to becoming a trans boy. But these actions also, in some deviant ways, permitted me to pursue my desired identity in mathematics and sport where I was often a source of celebration.

Burke and Stets (2009) name these interconnected ways to view reifications of identity in three umbrella terms of identity: role identity, social identity, and person identity. Role identity is based on the position a person occupies in each space, such as a math student during a mathematics class or a soccer player on a pitch. Social identity revolves around membership in certain groups and creates people who are dubbed “in” or “out” by the members of the groups (Burke & Stets, 2009). In a school setting, a person who is deemed to be good at mathematics might be labeled with something negative like, “geek” or “nerd”; however, an athlete might be labeled with something seen as positive such as, “fast” or “strong.” For a trans boy like me, both of those labels felt masculine and so reinforced my identity as a boy.

Adolescence

Most people find adolescence difficult; however, for me, the time was even more complicated as I was in a constant battle with my body, resisting the physical changes through athletic endeavors. This was the one span in my life where I did not care about excelling in mathematics and chose to focus almost exclusively on sport. Instead of taking my placement in pre-Algebra as a 7th grader, I went into regular math where I knew I would

Figure 4. Kyle Whipple, age 9, Blue Springs Basketball League

Figure 5. Kyle Whipple, age 14, Blue Springs Softball Association

not have homework and would therefore have more time for practice. Running, lifting weights, and the general physical workouts that came with sports kept my body fit and trim which meant almost no breast development and not starting a period until after my 14th birthday, and even once they started, they were intermittent.

Figure 6. Kyle Whipple, age 18, Blue Springs High School Volleyball

both volleyball and softball. In the winter months of 1988-1989, I tried out for and made a regional all-star volleyball team that played in tournaments every weekend. By my senior year I was in Math Analysis, Advanced Placement Calculus, and Physics while once again varsity lettering in volleyball and softball. I was quickly dubbed a “math geek” and “jock” and was happy to be associated with two groups that were so clearly masculine.

Leonard (2003) argues that identities are created through our social networks and institutions, such as school, marriage, family, and friends. During my adolescence, the physical changes that came with puberty forced me into trying to meet social norms for women in those institutions while also wanting to live authentically as a man. The discourses of gender, mathematics, and athletics exposed the notions of multiple identities within which I could exist and grow differently from the socio-cultural norms (Gergen, 2000). Being a

Figure 7. Kyle Whipple, age 18, Blue Springs High School Softball

Within this same span, the number of opportunities adolescents are allowed for athletic play start to dwindle. Sports teams are divided into gendered groupings (no matter what the skill levels are) and fewer and fewer adolescents make the team. By the first year of high school, while students are 14 years old, many teams are created through systems of tryouts with only the most skilled allowed to play. Because of the intensity with which one starts to focus on two or three sports, other sports drop away. As a freshman I was placed with a particularly inspirational Algebra I teacher who convinced me I could have a future career in mathematics, so after my two-year hiatus, I delved back into the subject with passion. I had to balance being an athlete with being a strong student, but the combination helped me to focus on my masculinity and distracted me from the discomfort of my body. By my junior year, I took both Algebra II and Trigonometry while varsity lettering in

part of the school athletic teams was helpful in this regard as I had an outlet for physical energy and a way to fit in with a group. I learned the benefits of hard work, practice, and being a member of a team through both mathematics and my teams.

Athletics was my first introduction into setting goals and keeping track of achievements. My coaches highlighted the benefits of healthy living and how having a healthy body can help lead to better mental health. My high school volleyball coach went so far as to bring a sports psychologist to several practices to help us learn methods for relaxation and focus. For a person who felt like their body was betraying them, these types of sessions and the repetition of the importance of overall health was extremely useful. The confidence I gained because of these lessons helped me to share my identity with my family.

Coming Out

I knew that playing sports in college was going to help me stay focused in the same way it had in high school. I attended a small liberal arts college in the Midwest where I made the softball team and earned a degree in mathematics. However, it was only 1990 and I still did not have a word to describe who I was as a trans man. At this time, searching the internet was not an option, but I was lucky, I had a research-oriented girlfriend. During the summer after my sophomore year, we visited a large medical school library and after hours of searching through numerous texts, she finally found the word “transsexual” in a book. There was not even an entire chapter, but there was enough of a description for me to know that “transsexual” was the best description of my gender identity I had ever seen.

I decided to share this information with my parents, but I was terrified to talk to them in person. Instead, I wrote them each a personal note, which I left on their bedroom dresser. My dad had let me engage in numerous “boys only” sports as a child which made me feel like I could be more candid with him; for instance, he let me take boxing lessons and play football. However, my mom struggled with any variation from social norms, and I knew she would be more difficult to convince. The note to my dad was straightforward and his reaction was one of understanding and support. The note to my mom was softer as I wanted her to know I understood why this revelation would be difficult for her. My mom’s reaction was one of sadness and frustration; she tried several times to provide me with information on lesbians because she felt being homosexual would be an easier path for me. During these discussions my mom blamed her parenting skills, which was a common reason therapists at the time gave for the existence of gay or lesbian children. Finally, my parents decided counseling

Figure 8. Kyle Whipple, age 19, Northeast Missouri State University Softball

was the best course of action and they made an appointment for me with a therapist, who proudly included his religious beliefs in his work, but who also dealt with lesbian and gay teenagers. After meeting with him for an hour once per week for about six weeks, I stopped going. The sessions were focused on how I should be working to make myself feel more attracted to men (what we call conversion therapy today) and the problems I had with my father. When I refused to give my father a letter the therapist had me write detailing the ways he had failed me, the therapist told me I was too immature for his treatments to work.

My mom's next course of action was for me to see an endocrinologist believing that my issues must be hormone related. I saw that doctor twice and he believed me when I revealed that I was transsexual. Having professional confirmation and advice felt like a tremendous first step on the road to my transition. I was extremely excited about transitioning because in my 19-year-old mind, I was going to be taking hormone replacement therapy (HRT) and having gender affirmation surgery (GAS) before I headed back to college in the fall. In my second appointment he said,

“You are transsexual. You should not feel bad about it, there is nothing that causes these types of things, they just happen sometimes. Colorado is the closest place that you can receive treatment. We don't do it here.”

My world collapsed. There was no way I could move to Colorado; I simply did not have the funds. I fell into a severe depression that led to self-destructive behaviors like quitting the softball team, taking up smoking, and engaging in self-harm and suicidal ideation that caused a rift between my parents and myself. I blamed them for not providing me with the means to obtain medical care I felt was necessary and was frustrated they believed any type of therapy would be beneficial. I was incredibly angry, an anger that develops and takes years to learn how to handle, and became difficult to be around, lashing out, both verbally and physically, at those around me for the smallest of mistakes and causing most people to withdraw.

Before the start of the fall semester, my mom found a therapist willing to work with me for the academic year. I saw the new therapist once per month for my junior year. I concentrated heavily on my mathematics courses because I saw them as my path to a job that could possibly lead to funding my transition. Solving problems and working on proofs became my escape from the reality of my situation. The assignments were safe with the rules of mathematics to lead from one step to another, and working in isolation was an accepted part of the identity of mathematician.

During these years, there was clearly a struggle in the development of my identity. I wanted to present myself as a person who was in control of his self-identity; but this was obviously in conflict with what I was going through. Wenger (1998) describes the construction of identities through a constant reformation and renaming as members of various communities into one identity. At one moment I felt powerful with my identities but at other moments I felt powerless. This kind of dynamic interplay with my work in mathematics and my social position also suggested a constant and evolving resistance to the existing power norms (Foucault, 1984).

Adult

As I moved into early adulthood, I realized a transition was many years away due to my socioeconomic status. Once I graduated with my BA in mathematics, I decided to enter graduate school to pursue an MA in mathematics. As a part of my degree, I was awarded a position as a teaching assistant which made me realize I enjoyed teaching more than I enjoyed theoretical mathematics. With that in mind, I changed my major to mathematics education, and upon graduation I accepted a teaching and coaching position in a rural town within driving distance of where I had attended college. Because the small town was predictably conservative, I hid my identity. Not being my true self was emotionally difficult and caused me to struggle with anger once again. I distracted myself by diving into the work of preparing for five different courses and

three different sports to coach. However, I knew I could not continue to exist in that false state forever, so I moved on in my career after just three years.

Figure 9. Kyle Whipple, age 36, Kirksville High School Softball Coach

In conjunction with the growth of my mathematics teacher and coach identities, I was also negotiating my sexuality and gender identities. I am a trans man who “has always known” which gender I most strongly identified with; nevertheless, I still had to negotiate my transness along with my identities of mathematics teacher and coach. Because mathematicians are stereotyped as masculine and rational,

and coaches are stereotyped as masculine, weaving in the trans man identity is seen as a natural fit; yet as a secondary teacher and coach, I was still not part of the norms.

I eventually accepted a mathematics teaching position, where I also coached softball, in the higher paying and larger school district where I lived. I spent the next 15 years teaching secondary mathematics, and I coached softball for the first 10 of those years. Teaching in a larger school meant fewer class preparations and more time for developing myself as a coach. I was finally able to start letting my identity out in small steps and embracing the social structures of schools, which, along with my personal life, helped to develop my math teacher identity (Hodges & Cady, 2012). All teachers negotiate their identities as they participate in classrooms through curriculum, instruction, and professional development (Hodges & Cady, 2012). Mathematics teachers can be viewed as a role identity, as society dubs people as “born to teach” and mathematics is often considered a subject that students “either get or don’t get,” and the role identity is then reinforced throughout the professional lives of the teachers.

Over the course of my 20-year teaching and coaching career, transgender people became more visible in society. Many doctors would prescribe hormone replacement therapy (HRT) and many surgeons would perform top surgery (bilateral mastectomy and chest reconstruction to create a masculine chest), but one still needed a letter from a therapist stating the choice had been carefully considered. I finally had the financial stability to pay for top surgery, so I found a therapist in a nearby larger city who was willing to talk to me about writing a letter for a surgeon. I was back in the office of a therapist who was focused on gay and lesbian issues. Once a month for six months I met with the therapist for an hour-long session. In the last session, the therapist gave me a letter to present to a surgeon to have my top surgery. The countdown began and I was in full anticipation of finally having a surgery I had wanted since I was an adolescent.

One important part of my ability to have top surgery was that during those 20 years of being a teacher and coach, my reputation as both was that of being successful and I had substantial professional capital. My mathematics students did extremely well on state and national standardized tests, and my softball teams had more than one record-breaking season. By the time

I scheduled the surgery, I was confident it would not impact my teaching position, but I did not feel the same way about coaching. I knew that even with all the capital I had within the community, I would never be allowed to continue to coach, especially a girl's sport, as a trans man. While coaching created a safety net for my masculine identity, that net only held up if the community continued to see me as a cis woman. So, I retired from coaching after the fall of 2010 season. The decision was difficult but clearly in my best interest and the best interest of my players as the issue of my queer, trans identity would overshadow their efforts on the field.

I scheduled the surgery for the beginning of summer so that I did not need any time away from the classroom, and I did not legally change my name as my goal was to avoid any gossip about my transformation at the beginning of the school year. Having established myself as a coach, almost everyone called me, "Coach" anyway, so I did not feel like changing my name was a key aspect of my masculinity within the school system. I talked to my administrators privately so they would know what to expect the upcoming fall. However, I still faced discriminatory behavior from a few faculty members and students.

There were a couple of faculty members who were difficult to deal with and after my top surgery who would only communicate with me if it was a requirement. For instance, they would not make eye contact if we passed in the hallway or

Figure 11. Kyle Whipple, age 38, Kirksville High School Mathematics Teacher

Figure 10. Kyle Whipple, age 37, Kirksville High School Softball Coach

exchange greetings if we happened to be in the workroom at the same time. The behavior was passive aggressive and made for a stressful work environment. Seeing them in mandatory meetings made me anxious in anticipation of their reactions to any of my contributions. Clearly, I was not alone with these anxieties, as a national survey on the climate of schools during the 2006-2007 academic

year found about half of LGBT teachers felt unsafe at school (Wright, 2010). School systems mirror societal beliefs, and the bizarre idea that a teacher can change or influence a child's sexuality or gender persists and impacts teachers with a real or perceived LGBTQ+ identity in negative ways throughout their careers (Blount, 2005).

While one could argue my entire teaching career was a disruption to cisgender, heterosexual norms, the disruption was more noticeable after my top surgery. During my career as a teacher and coach, I did not take HRT, which placed me firmly in the non-binary area of the gender spectrum; however, most students moved through my classes after my top surgery as if nothing had changed. Prior to the surgery, I made it clear to students I was an ally to the LGBTQ+ community through inclusive pedagogy and curriculum in my classroom, and participation in Genders and Sexualities Alliance (GSA) activities such as Day of Silence. The LGBTQ+ students still considered me a resource and would occasionally come to my room before or after school to chat. However, there were instances where students were particularly mean; for instance, when I was walking through the hall once I heard a student say, "Get a moral lifestyle choice." This behavior was to be expected given there were conservative students in the school; yet it was still jarring and ultimately played a role in my decision to leave teaching at the high school level to pursue my Ph.D.

Discussion

The discussion section covers the deeper research connected to trans lives and trans athletes. I present the anger issues I struggle with in the context of trans bans for health care, access to sports, and the use of bathrooms, and the impacts of those bans on trans lives. Finally, I write about mentorship and the role it may play in helping trans students and athletes to find success.

[Whipple] brought a unique style to the KHS dugout. [He] didn't yell and scream, or stomp and shout. [He] didn't bark at umpires either. (Hunsicker, 2010)

Anger

Growing up as a trans man was difficult for me. In my memories, there were moments of extreme joy when I believed transition was imminent and moments of massive disappointment when the reality of the costs of transition derailed plans. The most stressful events occurred when the disappointment followed the joy, and these events always included stages of depression and self-destructive behaviors. The frustration of the lack of resources and control was a tremendous burden.

The legislative attacks in the United States on trans rights and trans athletes over the past few years have only added to that frustration. For trans athletes alone, within a six-month period in 2021, more than 1,200 online news articles, public statements, and opinion pieces were published with most of them politicizing trans identities without including the voices of trans athletes, or even calling them by name (Baeth & Goorevich, 2023). When I consider my access to support systems such as a loving partner, therapy, a social network, mentorship, and secure employment, I cannot help but feel like I won a trans lottery. I live in a state that is considered a refuge for trans people under attack across the United States (Karnowski, 2023). And yet, I am still dealing with intense anger issues. How would my life have been different if I had no access to athletics, I never met the lifelong mentor who started steering me down the right path at age 14, a lifetime without access to medical care including therapy, or any other support systems I needed? Lucky for me, I had all those things and have managed to become a highly functioning adult, even though my life is far from easy.

Trans Issues

Mathematics was a school subject in which I could be successful in isolation; I could hide my trans man identity behind facts and proofs. Playing sports and living as an athlete gave me positive reinforcement in ways that were decidedly masculine and provided a physical outlet for my anger issues. But I also must give credit to my mom for providing me a path through the most difficult times of my youth by finding an appropriate therapist. Finding a therapist to work with gender dysphoria in the late 1980s through the early 1990s was not easy. My mom spent time making phone calls which would lead to more phone calls before she settled for someone who was known for their work with gay and lesbian clients in the small town where I was attending college. I was reluctant to start after the experience with the therapist using conversion techniques, but this new therapist was different. She listened and offered strategies to deal with anger and never insinuated that she did not believe me about my trans identity.

The number of states passing laws preventing trans people from having access to medical care and athletics is disheartening to say the least. Any accurate accounting of trans healthcare will show that access is already very limited, particularly given the commonality of class barriers such as those I experienced (Bradford et al., 2013). When I think about the importance of athletics in my survival, I shudder to consider my youth without them. Granted, while my situation is different from that of trans girls who are most often the targets of such discriminatory legislation, it still pains me to think of their lack of access to a social network and positive mentorship, both of which I received through athletics. Baeth and Goorevich (2023) argue that trans women are specifically being used by conservative politicians in the United States to induce fear and create a moral panic amongst their voters so the politicians may act as “moral entrepreneurs” and enact laws claiming to protect cis women (p. 138). The reality is that these laws actually harm any cis women athletes who may be seen as “too masculine” by requiring invasive medical examinations.

Mentorship

One of the most important aspects of my story is the mentorship I received from my high school algebra teacher. His consistent belief in my mathematics ability combined with his acceptance of me for who I am, gave me the confidence I needed to pursue a mathematics degree and play college level varsity softball. Over my lifetime, I met every fork in the road with his encouragement and support. From being a young and immature high school freshman deciding that college was not out of my grasp, to deciding to pursue a Ph.D. in a city far from my comfort zone with a robust LGBTQ+ population, my mentor provided the inspiration I needed. I carried what I learned from that relationship into my mathematics teaching and coaching to provide the same type of support and reinforcement to my students and players. One of the players on my softball team for several years was an outstanding pitcher; yet, before almost every game she would pull me aside and almost whisper, “Are we going to beat this team?” And I would always reply, “Yes, yes we are.” Some players need that vote of confidence before every game and all adolescents can use the support of a lifelong mentor.

One of my more visible moments of mentorship happened when another team from our conference made it to the final four in state the same year we did. They beat us in the semi-finals, and we went on to win our game for 3rd place. Because the championship game was being played immediately after our win, we stayed to cheer for our conference rival. After all, the most exciting moments in sports happen when one outstanding opponent shows tremendous respect for another. When I announced my retirement shortly after this final game, the newspaper editor in town wrote an opinion piece about my coaching that included this:

A few weeks ago, I received this excerpt of an email. It was originally sent from the superintendent of the Boonville Public Schools to the Kirksville High School Activities Coordinator.

“I have been very involved in athletics throughout my 18-year career in education. During that time as a player, coach, and parent I have seen great sportsmanship and unfortunately very poor sportsmanship. I wanted to let you know that the support given to the Boonville Lady Pirates from the Kirksville Lady Tigers softball team on Saturday in the State Title Game was one of the greatest acts of sportsmanship I have seen. The girls from Kirksville were some of our biggest cheerleaders. They were leading chants, the wave, and getting our team fired up! You should be very proud of this outstanding group of ladies. They are what makes high school athletics great!”

With that said, does KHS softball coach [Kyle Whipple] deserve all the credit for [his] team's outpouring of support? Probably not, but after watching [Whipple] coach for the last several years, hearing a story that [his] players would do that for a conference rival who just a day earlier ended their state championship hopes, I can't say I was surprised.” (Hunsicker, 2010)

This article went on to describe the culture I created in both the dugout when I was coaching and the classroom when I was teaching. I cultivated relationships based on mutual respect with my students and players deriving from the empathy I displayed for the struggles they went through while developing their identities, the majority of which would not be completely formed until well after they left my classroom or dugout.

Instead, [he] was a positive, relaxed force, and under [his] guidance in that atmosphere, [his] players developed and reached for their full potentials. So, while the Lady Tigers have been blessed with talent in recent years, it's hard to believe a coach with the opposite characteristics would have led the program on not only its most successful run of all time, but arguably the most successful run of any sports program in KHS history. (Hunsicker, 2010)

These comments reveal what is lost to our communities when we ostracize and demonize trans people. Had I been excluded from youth sports, I would not have gone on to teach thousands of mathematics students and coach hundreds of players in ways that modeled fairness, camaraderie, and sportsmanship. Given the current climate of fear, would my mentor have stepped forward to guide me into healthy outlets for my anger? I believe wholeheartedly that he would have, but the hostile climate that bans create make it harder for young people to find mentors.

Conclusion

There is no such thing as a single-issue struggle because we do not lead single issue lives.

—Audre Lorde (1982), *Sister Outsider*

This autoethnography details three significant events in my journey as a trans man to becoming a secondary mathematics teacher and softball coach. The subject area of mathematics was an important part of my path as it provided me with both an entrance into a field dominated by men and the ability to find success in isolation. Playing sports as a child and eventually coaching a team offered opportunities for my masculinity to be an asset. Both mathematics and athletics saved my life in their own way. The voices of trans athletes, youth athletes, and LGBTQ+ inclusive

educators and coaches are missing from the current discourse around bans of trans athletes. I hope my story provides one such voice.

Mathematics education researchers have explored and wondered about gender equity and greater female participation in mathematics at all levels (Eccles & Wang, 2016; Ellison & Swanson, 2010). The effects of gender in mathematics education disproportionately affect girls resulting in lower mathematics grades, self-confidence, and interest, as well as higher anxiety and more negative attitudes (Cimpian et al., 2016; Fennema & Leder, 1990). Research also shows girls receive less support and encouragement from parents and teachers (Downey & Vogt Yuan, 2005; Eccles & Wang, 2016; Ellison & Swanson, 2010). These factors accumulate over time and push girls and women to choose careers in mathematics-related fields in lower proportions despite their qualifications (Eccles & Wang 2016). The focus of these studies has been on female participation and achievement, while the voices of LGBTQ+ teachers and students are missing in this work. I believe extending current gender studies in mathematics education would help researchers better understand how to help people of all genders succeed in mathematics.

A parallel argument to girls in mathematics education can be made for trans athletes in sport: just as girls have been excluded from mathematics content, trans children are excluded from athletic competition. Because there are so few trans athletes, it is easy for the media and politicians to position them as “spectres” who “haunt” their cisgender opponents (Baeth & Goorevich, 2023). Yet, no one in the media seems interested in telling stories of sports playing an important role in saving the lives of trans athletes. We know that there are mental health benefits to exercise and that sports also give young people the chance to learn how to overcome adversity, to work as a team, and to persist after a loss. And even worse, there is no broad public backlash against laws banning children as young as five years old from participating, an age where many youth leagues do not even divide teams by gender. Baeth & Goorevich (2023) argue “despite claims of protection, we speculate this moral panic, as others before, will not protect cisgender (and certainly not trans) women in sport. Rather, it will replicate prevailing power systems that have historically stymied the potential for gender equity in sports” (p. 146).

Just as gender is a complex and dynamic social force, sexual orientation is an equally complex and dynamic force that affects sociocultural interaction. This includes participation in many mathematics learning and teaching contexts, as well as athletic competitions. This autoethnography expands the findings of gender studies in mathematics education and athletics into a trans context. The fact that I received positive reinforcement for my athletic and mathematical skills, not despite, but because of my perceived distance from feminine gender norms is telling. Learning how to work as part of a team, as well as developing independent thinking and problem-solving skills required for upper-level mathematics courses, were both key to my successes as a teacher and coach. I believe research in gender and sexuality exploration in mathematics education and athletics needs to extend to the trans population to make teaching and learning mathematics, and participation in sport, more equitable, socially just, and inclusive.

The news that [Whipple] is stepping down from the KHS helm after taking the team to four Final Fours in the last five seasons is one that should be met with sadness not only for the athletic community, but the Kirksville community as a whole. It's people like [Whipple] who play such important roles in a youth's development, not only by achieving success on the field, but teaching them to be a better person off it. (Hunsicker, 2010)

Afterword: Dialogue Between Scholars

The video afterword between author and open reviewer is at: <http://youtu.be/6LhjWJdsuHk>.

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